

CASE STUDY: TULCEA

This policy brief is an outcome of the NEVERMORE project. It was developed through a multi-step process that combined the characterization of the Tulcea region, the definition of key policy storylines, expert consultations, and stakeholder surveys on implementation barriers and enablers. The effect of selected policies on key indicators was simulated using System Dynamics modelling, with an implementation period from 2030 to 2045 and two climate change scenarios (SSP2-4.5, an intermediate greenhouse gas emissions scenario, and SSP5-8.5, a very high greenhouse gas emissions scenario). Results from model simulations and the insights gathered throughout the process are the basis for the technical and policy recommendations presented in this brief.

Key Messages

Tulcea County includes the Danube Delta Biosphere Reserve which is increasingly hit by droughts, floods, storms and coastal erosion, affecting rural livelihoods, tourism, and ecosystems. Protecting and restoring forest and wetland ecosystems are fundamental to preserve biodiversity and provide key ecosystem services. Raising adaptive capacity through education and training, greener urban planning and targeted flood protection is crucial, as well as protecting agriculture with diversification and resource use efficiency. Resilience and sustainability of the tourism sector can be increased through deseasonalization, improvements in infrastructure, and decarbonization that can be achieved by increasing energy efficiency and transition to renewables.

Tulcea County is situated in the South-East of Romania, in Dobrogea region, being bordered by the Danube and Black Sea. It includes the large and thinly-populated Danube Delta, which is critically important due to its geographical position, natural resources, ethnic and cultural diversity, as well as its economic and tourism potential (yet unexploited). The climate is continental, with low precipitation, high atmospheric humidity in the delta area, hot summers and cold winters, often marked by blizzards. In the past decade, Tulcea has experienced several climate-related hazards, particularly droughts, floods, storms and coastal erosion.

Main economic sectors, challenges, and priorities

Agriculture: The economic development of Tulcea county is highly influenced by the Danube Delta Biosphere Reserve (DDBRA). Agriculture must comply with environmental restrictions related to protected areas. Inside the hinterland, agriculture is an important source of income for the rural community. Thus, drought and desertification processes pose a great challenge to rural livelihoods.

Forest: Forestry within the Danube Delta has had a rather checkered history, mainly due to the use of inappropriate species to create plantations. Plantation forests cover 5,400 ha, but this area is set to decline as the trees are endangered by natural pests that are activated by higher temperatures and drought. Thus, forests are encouraged to regenerate naturally. As they provide important harbours for biodiversity, forests cannot be used for wood production within the Biosphere Reserve area. Forests of economic interest are concentrated in the fluvial delta, outside of the protected area. Forestry absorbs a small fraction of the labour force in the DDBR.

Energy: Dobrogea is considered one of the most promising regions in Europe in terms of wind potential. The South East area between the Danube and the Black Sea has an average wind intensity of 7.2 m/s throughout the year, representing an ideal place for the location of wind turbines. In addition to the permanent and constant intensity of the wind, Dobrogea also has a favourable relief for the wind industry. The territory is relatively flat and the population density is low.

Tourism: Tourism in Tulcea revolves around its natural and archaeological sites, and historical monuments. In particular, the Danube Delta is a biosphere reserve; a true “living museum”; of biodiversity that includes 30 types of ecosystems more than 5000 species, and one of the largest wetlands in the world.

Water: Municipal waste, agricultural and industrial activities, as well as upstream sludge collection and disposal from sewage treatment plants are potential sources of pollution in the Danube Delta. This is partly due to the lack of adequate infrastructure, as the purification of domestic and industrial wastewater is carried out mechanically in the isolated rural communities where a centralized sewage system is lacking. Another important source of water pollution is the naval transport activity, due to the fact that not all ships and speed boats are equipped with efficient oil residue separators.

Priorities: Tulcea’s main priorities are related to the characteristic ecological features of the Danube Delta region. Technological development is seen as a key for both adaptation and mitigation actions, and the focus is on efficiency and innovation. Sustainable management of wetland areas is needed to preserve biodiversity, while balancing human habitation and economic use.

Decision-making and implementation context

Climate change adaptation and mitigation are addressed by county councils and regional agencies, in line with national policies. Vertical coordination across governance levels is weak, with fragmented implementation and unclear responsibilities being reported. Universities, research institutes, and community associations contribute to climate adaptation and mitigation efforts although no formal participatory process exists. Climate actions are funded primarily by national and regional grants, with some use of local climate funds and public-private partnerships. However, financial resources are insufficient or difficult to access due to the lack of local support agencies.

Technical and policy recommendations

1. Increase the capacity to adapt

Flood defences can reduce economic losses due to floods, although to a small extent. At the same time, the adaptive capacity of Tulcea’s population can be increased by providing education and training, while sensitivity can be minimized by improving green urban planning. A high implementation of such policies, supported by substantial incentives for education and training, can reduce climate-related risks for Tulcea’s population to zero even under the most adverse future climate scenario. Maximum benefits can be obtained by providing education and training to more than 50% of the population and implementing green urban areas on more than 30 km² in the region. This type of policies can be supported by a mix of local and European financing mechanisms, although current financial incentives are deemed to be insufficient.

Risk index for Tulcea’s population (0-1) under baseline and policy scenarios. It is calculated accounting for the probability of heatwaves, the exposed population, and their sensitivity and adaptive capacity.
Dmnl=dimensionless

Policies	Low	Medium	High
flood defences in urban areas	yes	yes	yes
Green urban planning	10	30	50
Education and training (% of population)	20	50	80

2. Protect agricultural production through improved cropland and water management

Tulcea’s agricultural production can be preserved by diversifying the production, increasing water availability and use efficiency, as well as investing in crop adaptation. Increasing water storage in agricultural land is key to face water scarcity in the region, although the area available for crop production would be reduced. Crop diversification and increased water availability can reduce crops sensitivity to climate hazards, with the best results obtained with a high level of policy implementation, i.e. more than 50% of crop diversification and increased water use efficiency. At the same time, substantial incentives are needed to promote the implementation of adaptation policies for the agricultural sector.

Policies	Low	Medium	High
Investments in crop adaptation (million €)	10	50	100
Crop diversification (% of cropland)	20	50	80
Efficient water demand from agriculture (% reduction)	20	50	80
Water storage increase (Hm 3)	10	30	50

Risk index for crops in Tulcea (0-1). It is calculated accounting for the drought exceedance probability, the ratio of exposed crops, as well as crops sensitivity and adaptive capacity. Dmnl=dimensionless

3. Sustainable use of water resources

The use of water resources in Tulcea can be optimized with a comprehensive integrated water policy, aimed at increasing water availability as well as reducing water demand from different sectors. Although water availability is not limited in the region, reducing water demand from the agricultural, industrial and urban sectors would reduce water pollution and increase the overall resource-use efficiency. The implementation of policies aimed at improving water use efficiency and quality, however, is constrained by high investment costs and lack of infrastructure, and requires institutional and financial support.

4. A resilient and diversified tourism sector

Tourism in Tulcea can increase its capacity to cope with climate related hazards, while also increasing its sustainability, by deseasonalizing tourist flows and investing in infrastructure. The risk index for tourism increases with the exposure to climate hazards; spreading tourist flows throughout the year and investing in adaptation and resilience not only can reduce risks but also increase revenues. Policies that promote resilient infrastructure with sustained investments can counteract the decline in tourist capacity. Indeed, high investment costs and limited access to infrastructure and technology limit the implementation of policies for a resilient and diversified tourism sector in Tulcea. Thus, institutional and financial support should be granted, supporting the development of resilient infrastructure.

Policies	Low	Medium	High
Promote domestic tourism (% increase of national tourists on the total)	20	50	80
Promote all year tourism (% of seasonal spread)	20	50	80
Investment in touristic infrastructure (% increase)	20	50	80

a) Risk index for tourism (0-1) and b) tourism income (billion euros) in Tulcea for baseline and policy scenarios. The risk index is calculated by combining the number of days with extreme events, the exposure of tourism assets (accommodations), and the sensitivity and adaptive capacity of the tourism sector, which together define its vulnerability. Dmnl=dimensionless

5. A more efficient use of energy for climate change mitigation and adaptation

Climate change adaptation and mitigation go hand in hand, so that improving resource use efficiency can both increase resilience and reduce emissions. Increasing energy efficiency by 30% can substantially reduce energy consumption in Tulcea, supporting a transformative transition to renewables. Such policies would enable drastic reductions in CO₂ emissions from the energy sector, which currently relies on renewables by as little as 10% of total energy production. A lower demand for energy and phasing out coal, oil and gas as energy sources would be beneficial in terms of self-sufficiency and resilience, which is crucial in times of high instability. Financial and institutional support are key drivers for the implementation of such policies, ensuring access to infrastructure and technology.

Policies	Low	Medium	High
Energy efficiency (% increase)	10	20	30
Energy transition model	Gradual	Good	Best
Incentives for energy efficiency and lower emissions	Low	Medium	High

6. A pathway to decarbonization

Although climate change adaptation is often prioritized at the local level, mitigation actions are nonetheless urgent. A switch to clean energy, increasing solar, wind and hydrogen capacity while reducing non-renewables would contribute to a low-carbon future as well as increase total energy production in Tulcea. Indeed, a high implementation of renewable energy policies would reverse the declining trend observed with the baseline and lower ambition scenarios. In particular, increasing solar and wind capacity by 200 and 60 MWh, respectively, would reduce the need for energy imports by 47% compared with the baseline in 2060. Financial and institutional support are key drivers for the implementation of such policies, ensuring access to infrastructure and technology.

Total energy consumption (million MWh) in Tulcea for baseline and policy scenarios under a) SSP2-4.5 and b) SSP5-8.5 climate scenarios.

Policies	Low	Medium	High
Solar capacity increase (MWh,)	50	100	200
Wind capacity increase (MWh)	20	40	60
Reduction in non-renewables production (MWh)	1	3	5
Incentives for renewables and carbon tax	None	Low	Medium

a) Total energy production and b) energy imports in Tulcea under baseline and policy scenarios

7. Protect ecosystems for climate change adaptation and mitigation

Tulcea is home to the most important protected areas in Romania, with wetland and forest. Protecting and restoring these ecosystems is key to preserve biodiversity and keep providing key ecosystem services, including ones related to climate change adaptation and mitigation. Key actions include expanding protected wetland and forest areas, promoting afforestation, and improving forest management through sustainable biomass use. Incentivizing afforestation can lead to an increase in forest area by up to 6% by 2060, while increasing protected areas would limit agricultural expansion and reduce the decline in wetlands. Further, a high implementation of afforestation and forest management measures would reverse the decline in forest carbon storage, contributing to mitigation efforts. High investment costs and limited access to infrastructure and technology are major barriers to the implementation of these policies. Thus, adequate funding and supportive regulations should be provided, streamlining funding opportunities, investing in capacity-building for land managers, and strengthening monitoring and enforcement while simplifying bureaucratic procedures.

Policies	Low	Medium	High
Protected forest land increase (km ²)	10	20	30
Protected wetland area increase (km ²)	2	4	6
Improved forest management (%increase)	20	50	80
Incentives for afforestation and forest management	Low	Medium	High

a) Total forest area and b) protected forest area in Tulcea for baseline and policy scenarios.

a) Total wetland area and b) protected wetland area in Tulcea for baseline and policy scenarios.

Conclusions:

Tulcea's pathway is a "green technology" transition: protect wetlands, forests and biodiversity while modernizing water, agriculture, tourism and energy systems. Delivery relies on clearer responsibilities, stronger coordination, streamlined procedures, and sustained technical and financial support so local actors can access funding and implement at scale.

CATALOGUE & LOCAL TOOL

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